

Methodology for fast testing of carbon-based nanostructured 3D electrodes in vanadium redox flow battery

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Vanadium redox flow battery
Nanostructured carbon electrodes
Single-cell performance
Electrochemical characterization
Load curve

ABSTRACT

Progress in material chemistry is manifested daily by the variety of prepared functional materials, often with nanodimensional structuring. The electrodes for vanadium redox flow batteries have been shown to benefit from incorporating nanostructured materials such as carbon nanotubes. However, the methods of such incorporation are far from optimal, relying mainly on physical deposition or insertion into a binder. Here, we describe a technique for integrating carbon-based rod-like nanomaterials into a vanadium redox flow battery and a methodology for fast nanomaterial performance testing. The technique is based on creating a fixed nanomaterial bed sandwiched between two graphite felt electrodes, forming a 3D flow-through electrode in the battery. Performing various positive and negative control experiments, we show the beneficial effect of a nanostructured bed on the primary battery characteristics obtained from short-term electrochemical experiments. We characterize carbon nanotubes exhibiting promising electrochemical behavior in vanadium electrolytes, as observed in our previous study. The load curves obtained from charge-discharge steps at various current densities and electrolyte flow rates revealed considerable differences in the performance of the tested materials, with few-walled carbon nanotubes reaching unsurpassable characteristics. At room temperature, with 50 %-SOC-working solutions and the highest tested linear velocity of 14.6 cm/min, the evaluated power density for this material reached values above 500 mW/cm². For comparison, thermally treated graphite felt, used as a benchmark material, provided a power density of around 300 mW/cm² under identical conditions. Although developed for vanadium redox flow batteries, the method enables testing tube-like and rod-like (nano-)materials for flow electrochemical systems.

1. Introduction

Recent socioeconomic developments, driven by the energetic crisis and climate change, underscore the urgent need to ensure a sufficient supply of renewable electric energy. However, highly unpredictable and inherently variable energy production handicaps renewable sources compared to traditional power stations, providing a stable and adjustable power output [1]. Efficient storage of renewable energy during its overproduction and seamless supply during high-demand periods is, thus, necessary [2,3]. Allowing for such requirements, new electric energy storage systems for storing/releasing large quantities of electric energy from renewable sources are developing rapidly [4].

Common electric energy storage strategies build on hydroelectrical, thermal, and electrochemical systems, the last known as batteries.

Currently, lithium-iron-phosphate batteries own the largest market share due to their installations with solar panels in households. The industrial use of LiFePO₄ batteries is limited due to the high investment cost and problems with the control of the power output [5]. From this perspective, redox flow batteries are a promising candidate for large-scale employment. Especially vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFBs), first designed by Skyllas-Kazacos during the 1980s [6], are gaining attention. The overall reaction proceeding in VFBRs (equ. 1) generates a standard cell voltage $E_0 = 1.259$ V:

Scalability, adaptive energy capacity, power output control, long cycle life, and low maintenance requirements are the major advantages of VRFBs [7]. Adversely, the limited vanadium solubility imparts VRFBs

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2024.144681>

Received 16 April 2024; Received in revised form 28 June 2024; Accepted 5 July 2024

Available online 6 July 2024

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Table 1

List of carbon-based electrode materials used during the experimental part.

Name	Purchased from	LOT#	$ \Delta E_{V^{4+} \leftrightarrow V^{5+}} [V]$	$ \Delta E_{V^{2+} \leftrightarrow V^{3+}} [V]$
Graphite felt: pristine, ground (UT-GFE), thickness: 5 mm	Provided by Pinflow Energy Storage s.r.o.	–	$0,433 \pm 0,075$	$0,397 \pm 0,041$
Graphite felt: thermally treated, ground (TT-GFE), thickness: 5 mm	Provided by Pinflow Energy Storage s.r.o.	–	$0,237 \pm 0,019$	$0,151 \pm 0,057$
Carbon nanotubes: multi-walled (MWCNT)	Sigma Aldrich (code: 659,258–10 G)	308,068–56–6	$0,081 \pm 0,008$	$0,069 \pm 0,009$
Carbon nanotubes: multiwalled, carboxylic acid functionalized (f-MWCNT)	Sigma Aldrich (code: 755,125–1 g)	BCBZ9473	$0,147 \pm 0,044$	$0,134 \pm 0,051$
Carbon nanotubes: few-walled (FWCNT)	Sigma Aldrich (code: 900,788 – 250 mg)	MKCD5241	$0,126 \pm 0,005$	$0,107 \pm 0,006$

Fig. 1. 3D schematics of the functional components of the flow-through electrochemical cell.

with a relatively low energy density of 20 to 33 Wh/L [8] that must be compensated by the size of electrolyte storage tanks [9]. Also, the high cost of perfluorinated ion-exchange membranes and vanadium electrolytes shall be considered before installation [10]. Electrode material strongly influences the battery performance. Chemical stability, mechanical strength, electronic conductivity, and electrochemical activity towards vanadium reactions are crucial in selecting the electrode [11–13]. For example, metallic electrodes, previously employed in VRFBs, underwent surface passivation, rendering them unsuitable for the application [14]. Today, carbon-based materials are commonly used to construct both positive and negative electrodes [15]. Usually, graphite felt electrodes (GFEs) bearing various physical and chemical modifications are used for this purpose [16,17]. Porous carbon electrodes, possessing large reactive surfaces, show great promise in improving vanadium-based electrochemistry [18–20]. Enabled by the advances in nanomaterial synthesis during recent decades, new electrode materials possessing enhanced electrical conductivity and mechanical strength are being developed. For example, a cylindrical fullerene, known as carbon nanotubes (CNTs), is a promising candidate. It possesses superior conductivity, tensile strength, chemical resistance to highly acidic environments, and intrinsically large electrochemically active surfaces available for vanadium redox reactions, potentially leading to higher current density operation of the cell [21]. Chemical modifications of CNTs introducing carboxylic acid or hydroxylamine groups increased material hydrophilicity and enhanced reaction kinetics, enabling higher current densities [22]. Nitrogen-doped GFE was reported to catalyze the vanadium redox reactions, specifically the VO_2^+ / VO^{2+} reaction [23–27]. This observation partially agrees with the results obtained in our previous work where nitrogen-doped carbon nanotubes (ND-MWCNT) showed reasonable catalytic activity towards vanadium electrochemistry [28]. However, the voltammogram for ND-MWCNT also revealed its averaged performance in terms of current peaks (when compared to other materials) and poor reaction reversibility. These observations suggest that it is not straightforward and easy to generalize experimental results, forcing the researchers to characterize each synthesized material for a given application.

Although CNTs are a promising electrode material, the difficulties with their mechanical stability on commercially used conductive

substrates (usually GFE) still prevent their employment on a larger scale. Different approaches to integrating CNTs into VRFBs as working electrodes were attempted [29]. Physical CNT deposition by drying the nanomaterial dispersion on GFE or their direct synthesis on GFE by chemical vapor deposition belong to straightforward methods [30,31]. Other possibilities include electrochemical deposition or the use of binders (e.g., poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) or polyethyleneimine (PEI) creating conductive membrane electrodes [32]. Sodium carboxymethylcellulose (NaCMC), forming a porous composite with CNTs or CNT/PVDF conductive membranes, was used in other batteries, such as lithium-ion or sodium-ion batteries [33–36]. Unfortunately, all these techniques intrinsically limit the CNTs performance by (i) lowering their available active surface area (partially hindered by binders), (ii) low mechanical stability on GFE (physical deposition), or (iii) creating only a thin CNT layer on the surface possessing feature of rather 2D (flat) than 3D electrode. An ideal scenario utilizes a fixed, flow-through bed of given CNTs, preserving the large electrochemically active surface area and minimizing the transport distances of electrochemically active species. Such a fixed bed, however, offers very high hydrodynamic resistance, resulting in enormous pressure drops, as theoretically predicted by Darcy's law with the Carman-Kozeny coefficient [37,38]. The problem with the electrolyte flow homogeneity through such a bed is a secondary effect - the flowing solution tends to bypass the bed by creating shortcutting channels.

To overcome these challenges, we propose an electrochemical cell housing a nanomaterial porous bed sandwiched between compressible graphite felts, forming a composite 3D electrode. The compression of the electrode system provides (i) good mechanical stability of the bed, (ii) good electrical contact with the bed, (iii) short transport distances to/from the nanomaterial bed, and (iv) good contact with porous GFE and sandwiching current collectors at a reasonable pressure drop. Here, we use the developed system for fast testing (screening) various carbon-based nanomaterials as prospective electrode materials in VRFBs, showing dramatic differences in their performance.

Fig. 2. a) the pressure drop obtained on the system (s1) and comparison with other systems, b) the detailed view of the measured pressure dependence on the linear velocity for systems (s2), (s3), and (s4).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and materials

Commercial vanadium electrolyte composed of 1.6 M vanadium sulfate (an equimolar vanadium mixture in oxidation states +3 and +4), 2 M sulfuric acid, and 0.3 wt.% phosphoric acid purchased from GfE (Germany) was used in all experiments. Perfluorinated sulfonic acid (PFSA) cation-exchange membrane (F-930-RFD) with a 30- μm -dry thickness was obtained from Fumatech (Germany). 3D printing resin UV DLP Tensile was purchased from PhotoCentric3D (United Kingdom). The MITOP FINET PES 3 filtration fabric from polyethersulfone (PES) was obtained from MiTOP a.s. (Czech Republic). The nanostructured materials listed in Table 1 were preselected based on the results reported in [28], investigating the nanostructured materials in a stationary cell by cyclic voltammetry. This pre-selection was primarily based on the peak currents and peak-to-peak potential separations. The peak-to-peak separations are given in Table 1.

The lowest ΔE_p for both vanadium reactions was observed for MWCNT, indicating the best reversibility. FWCNT exhibited the second-best performance. This material also demonstrated the best reproducibility. The poorest performance was observed with UT-GFE, which was used as one of the benchmarks for the current study.

2.2. Electrochemical flow-through cell

The electrochemical cell is a stack of multiple functional components (see Fig. 1), having 11 cm in length and 3.5 cm in width. The middle flow-through parts (6a and b in Fig. 1) accommodating the nanomaterial bed were designed in AutoCAD Fusion 360 and printed out on Prusa SL1S SPEED 3D printer from Liqcreate Flexible-X resin, possessing excellent compression resistance, tensile strength, and chemical stability in an acidic environment (see datasheets available on <https://www.liqcreate.com>). The copper current collectors (3a and b in Fig. 1) and carbon composite plates PPG86 (Eisenhuth, Germany; parts 4a and b in Fig. 1) contacting the nanomaterial bed were manufactured by micro-machining on a micro-milling machine GRAVOS GV21. 14 \times 7.5 cm duralumin plates (1a and b in Fig. 1), allowing tight system assembly, were also made by machining. The parts denoted as 5a, b, and 7a, b in Fig. 1 are silicone layers providing electric and hydraulic insulation. Parts 2 a and b are polycarbonate foils insulating duralumin plates from the copper current collectors.

The PFSA membrane (8 in Fig. 1) separating the anodic and cathodic parts of the cell is in direct contact with the 3D electrodes placed in the center of fluidic parts (6a and 6b in Fig. 1). The inlet and outlet of the fluidic parts are provided with a thread UNF 1/4"–28 G for fittings. The

membrane-3D electrode contact area is 0.5 cm². The other side of the 3D electrodes is pressed against carbon composite plates (4a and 4 b in Fig. 1) and copper current collectors (3a, 3b in Fig. 1) to couple the cell electrically to a potentiostat. The system is pressed together by two duralumin plates (1a, 1b in Fig. 1), tightened with a torque of 3 Nm set on a torque wrench.

Figures S1a and S1b show a detailed view of the 3D electrode and its integration into the fluidic parts (6a and b in Fig. 1). A block of tested nanomaterial (12 in Fig. S1) is sandwiched between two layers of untreated (pristine) graphite felt electrode (9a, and 9b in Fig. S1). Such an assembly was chosen based on results obtained in pressure drop tests, described in the result Section 3.1. To prevent the loss of nanomaterial during the electrolyte flow and mechanically stabilize the 3D electrode, we place filter fabrics (11 a and b in Fig. S1) at the electrode chamber inlet and outlet.

2.3. Experimental setup for single-cell testing

In the flow-through portion of the experimental setup, filtration fabrics measuring 0.8 \times 1.5 cm² were strategically positioned at both the inlet and outlet points, as previously detailed (see Fig. 2). 0.5 \times 1 cm² GFE with an uncompressed thickness of approximately 2.5 mm was placed at the bottom carbon composite plate, and the designated nanostructured material was carefully weighed and introduced on top. The upper GFE of the same thickness was placed atop the nanomaterial, thereby forming the previously described sandwich-type assembly for the flow-through system. The 2.5-mm-thick GFE was prepared from an original 5-mm GFE sheet by precise cutting. In the case of the ground/milled felts, a Retsch MM 400 oscillating mill set at a vibration frequency of 25 Hz was employed to comminute 10 g of GFE into a powdered form within 3 min. Ground GFE, a benchmark for nanomaterial testing, underwent the same experimental procedure outlined above.

The experimental system configuration was as follows (see Fig. S2). After the cell assembly, the electrochemical cell (16 in Fig. S2) was securely fastened using Dural plates, according to the description in Section 2.2. Tygon tubing, with an inner diameter of 1.52 mm, connected the inlet and outlet cell fittings with Teflon tubing leading to the storage flasks (17a, 17b in Fig. S2). Each flask contained 4 ml of vanadium electrolyte with the composition given in Section 2.1. The flasks 17a and 17b were inserted into larger GL45 screw-top bottles (18a, 18b in Fig. S2) with a volume of 100 ml. This arrangement facilitated keeping the stored solutions (especially the negative electrolyte) under a nitrogen atmosphere to prevent the spontaneous oxidation of V²⁺ species to V³⁺ (self-discharging). The electrolyte flow was regulated by an ISMATEC IPC-8 peristaltic pump (19 in Fig. S2). The experiment employed magnetic stirrers to maintain chemical homogeneity in the

electrolytes. Finally, the electrochemical cell was electrically connected to the potentiostat (20 in Fig. S2) with four clips.

2.4. Experimental setup for pressure drop measurement

Honeywell ABP pressure sensors purchased from Bartels mikro-technik (14a, 14b in Fig. S3) were inserted into T-shape fittings at the inlets (13a, 13b in Fig. S3) into the anodic and cathodic parts of the cell. The cell outlets (15a, 15b in Fig. S3) were open to the atmosphere. The experiments were performed with distilled water since the working vanadium electrolyte quickly damaged the sensors due to its corrosive character. We, therefore, estimated the pressure drops for the vanadium electrolyte by multiplying the measured value for water with a ratio of the vanadium electrolyte to water viscosities. We focused these experiments on evaluating pressure drops across 3D electrodes formed by nanomaterial only and 3D electrodes combining nanomaterial and carbon felt electrodes, as depicted in Fig. S1.

2.5. Electrochemical measurement of VRFB single-cell

All electrochemical measurements were conducted using the Potentiostat/Galvanostat Gamry Reference 600. The experiments mainly focused on reconstructing the battery polarization curves of the flow electrochemical cell for various nanostructured electrode materials and linear electrolyte velocities at room temperature. The sequence of those experiments was: (i) high-frequency impedance measurement of the assembled battery with fresh, uncharged electrolytes, (ii) charging the electrolytes to 50 % SOC, (iii) application of charging and discharging steps at various applied current densities. The details of each step are given below.

We performed the high-frequency impedance measurement over a frequency range from 10^0 to 10^4 Hz, with a signal amplitude of 50 mV at OCV, to determine the initial ohmic system resistance (ASR_{in}). Resistance was evaluated as an intercept of the spectrum with the x-axis in the high-frequency region of the Nyquist diagram. The resistance values were then recalculated into area-specific resistances (ASR) by multiplying the resistance value by the active membrane area.

The equimolar vanadium electrolyte was subjected to a charging process, eventually reaching a 50 % state-of-charge (SOC) by applying a constant current density load of 200 mA/cm^2 for 6175 s, corresponding to a passed charge of 171.5 mAh. The upper voltage limit was set at 1.85 V during the charging to prevent oxidative damage to the positive electrode and water-splitting reactions. The charging time was determined by Faraday's law, considering the electrolyte concentration of 1.6 M and an electrolyte volume of 4 ml in the storage flasks. Upon reaching 50 % SOC, we measured the open circuit voltage (OCV), getting an average value of 1.376 V.

Then, the system underwent cyclic application of charge/discharge steps with the following charge/discharge current densities: 50, 100, 150, 300, 500, and 750 mA/cm^2 . Each charging and discharging took 120 s, apart from the charging affected by the voltage limit of 1.85 V, which has been proportionately extended. Between these charging and discharging stages, an OCV stabilizing measurement taking 240 s was performed.

3. Results and discussion

The result section consists of two major parts. The first one is devoted to the development of the miniaturized flow-through battery and conducting proof-of-concept experiments justifying its use. The second part characterizes the performance of the tested nanostructured materials under several applied linear velocities and discusses the obtained results.

3.1. Pressure drop

As mentioned in the introduction, a nanomaterial bed usually offers high resistance to passing fluids, resulting in unsurpassable pressure drops. To quantify such pressure drops and subsequently justify the final design of the nanostructured bed used in further characterization studies, we performed pressure drop measurements across four electrode arrangements. These arrangements were: (s1) the flow-through electrode formed only by 30 mg of functionalized multiwalled carbon nanotubes (f-MWCNT), (s2) the flow-through electrode formed by 3 layers of pristine (untreated) unground GFE, (s3) the flow-through electrode formed by 30 mg of ground GFE placed between two pristine unground GFES (sandwich-type), and (s4) the flow-through electrode formed by 30 mg of f-MWCNT placed between two pristine GFES (sandwich-type). The pressure drop was measured at six linear velocities, specifically 2.48, 4.91, 7.33, 9.76, 12.18, and 14.61 cm/min . These velocities represent superficial velocities evaluated as a ratio of applied volumetric flow rates and a flow area of the electrode chamber equal to 0.4 cm^2 . The obtained results are plotted in Fig. 2.

The arrangement (s1), although the most tempting regarding the interfacial area and transport distances, proved unusable for our purpose. The pressure drop, even at the lowest applied flow rate, quickly reached the limit of the pressure sensors (116.3 kPa – see Fig. 2a), elucidating the tremendous difficulties with electrolyte leakage. Even when sealing the system properly, we observed limited performance of the (s1) arrangement in further tests. The limited performance was caused by flow inhomogeneity through the packed bed. The flowing solution created shortcut channels (seen after cell disassembly), indicating that most of the electrode surface was inactive.

The situation dramatically changed in the other three cases in which pieces of pristine (untreated) unground graphite felt electrode offered a reasonable resistance to the working electrolyte flow, albeit at the cost of the electrode surface and transport distances. The systems with pristine and ground GFE (s2 and s3) showed linear dependence of the pressure loss on the mean velocity (see Fig 2b). Slightly different behavior was observed for the f-MWCNTs sandwiched between two pieces of untreated unground graphite felt electrode (system s4). While pressure drops similar to those of systems (s2) and (s3) were observed at low flow velocities, the pressure loss grew faster at higher velocities, peaking at 4.39 kPa for 14.61 cm/min . This value was approximately twice as large as that for the systems (s2) and (s3). The relatively sudden change in the slope of the measured dependence was most probably associated with the flow-caused nanomaterial reorganization within the sandwich. Such reorganization was observed in older types of devices, resulting in electrolyte leakage and damage to the electrochemical cell. Due to the presence of the sandwich-type assembly, such sudden changes do not impede the functionality of the system but can still be detected through pressure drop measurements. This further underscores the importance of the mentioned fixation of nanomaterials in the flow-through electrochemical cell. As stated in Section 2.4, the pressure drop measurements were done with distilled water because of the corrosive nature of sulfuric acid. By considering the viscosity of the working electrolyte, we estimated the actual pressure drops with the working electrolyte to be approximately 2.6 times larger. However, the pressure losses in the sandwich system were relatively low and, thus, usable for the further development of the characterization method. Importantly, we did not observe leaks when performing experiments with the vanadium solutions.

Overall, these results stress the critical significance of the sandwich-type assembly configuration, wherein the nanomaterial is strategically positioned between two carbon-felt electrodes.

3.2. Effect of nanostructured material

After establishing the functional geometry of the electrode, we performed an experimental study revealing the effect of nanostructured

Fig. 3. Charging curves of vanadium electrolyte for ground graphite felt electrode (blue) and nanobed (red curve) in the cell with a current density of 200 mA/cm² at room temperature. The linear velocity of the electrolyte was 2.5 cm/min. The dashed line represents the limit set to prevent unwanted electrochemical reactions from occurring.

Fig. 4. Charge and discharge experiments with the nanobed and ground GFE electrodes. The vanadium working solution was charged to 50 % SOC. The electrolyte linear velocity was 2.5 cm/min. The measurement proceeded at room temperature.

material on the electrochemical behavior of the developed miniaturized battery system. To evaluate this effect, we experimentally compared the behavior of two selected systems. In this section, the two systems are called nanostructured bed (nanobed) and ground untreated (pristine) GFE. Specifically, the nanostructured bed was made of 30 mg of f-MWCNT sandwiched between two pieces of pristine graphite felt electrode. The referred amount of nanotubes was established empirically based on observations of the system when conducting preliminary experiments. For a given cell geometry, 30 mg of carbon nanotubes was an optimum, considering the electrode resistance and the feasibility of assembling the sandwich. When inserting a smaller amount of the material, poor contact with the carbon-polymer composite plate results in large ohmic resistances. Decreasing the resistance by increasing the compression force usually causes irreversible mechanical damage to the composite plate. Similarly, the weight of the ground GFE layer was 30 mg. The obtained results, thus, are intrinsically normalized to the weight of the tested layer. Such assembled electrodes were used in both the cathodic and anodic compartments of the electrochemical cell.

We followed the experimental protocol described in Section 2.5.

Specifically, we (i) determined the initial system ohmic resistance by measuring its high-frequency impedance, (ii) charged the working electrolytes to 50 % SOC by passing an electric current of 200 mA/cm² for 6175 s, and (iii) carried out charge/discharge step experiments at predefined current densities.

The initial ohmic resistances obtained from the impedance reading were 1.22 and 1.42 Ω for the nanobed and ground GFE, respectively. These values, related to the active surface of the membrane (0.5 cm²), translate into area-specific resistance of 0.61 and 0.71 Ωcm². The initial resistances of both systems showed similar values, suggesting they provide similar electronic and ionic conductivity. For comparison, we also tested 30 mg of an unground pristine GFE sandwiched between two GFE layers, having a substantially higher resistance of 2.18 Ωcm², most probably due to high interface resistances between the individual felt layers. Such a high value precluded such an electrode from further use since we could not charge the working solution without exceeding the voltage of 1.85 V.

3.2.1. Electrolyte charging

A constant current load of 200 mA/cm² was applied to the electrochemical cell to charge 4 ml of vanadium electrolyte on either side of the battery to 50 % SOC. As described in Section 2.5, we limited the maximum possible voltage applied to the system during charging to 1.85 V. This limitation reduced the risk of carbon composite plate degradation and water-splitting reactions.

The chronopotentiograms capturing the electrolyte charging for the nanobed and the ground GFE are plotted in Fig. 3. Surprisingly, the initial voltage needed to sustain the required charging current density of 200 mA/cm² was more than three times higher for the ground GFE than for the nanobed, although the initial ohmic resistances were almost identical. The observation implies that pristine GFE exhibits relatively low electrocatalytic activity towards vanadium species, requiring higher applied overvoltages for the reaction $V^{3+} \rightleftharpoons V^{4+}$, which proceeds in the initial half of the charging experiment. However, unlike the nanobed, the voltage does not change significantly during charging with ground GFE due to generally much higher overvoltages for initial charging reactions. In the case of the nanobed, the first fast voltage increase (within a few seconds) is probably associated with induced transport limitations and the second with electrochemical reaction thermodynamics and kinetics. Specifically, the overpotential for $V^{3+} \rightleftharpoons V^{4+}$ reaction (between 0 and cca 2500s in Fig. 3) is significantly smaller than in the case of ground GFE. Thus, with nanobed electrodes, we can see a voltage transition at 0 % SOC (around 2500s) where $V^{3+} \rightleftharpoons V^{2+}$ and $V^{4+} \rightleftharpoons V^{5+}$ reactions start to proceed at negative and positive electrodes, respectively. In the case of ground GFE electrodes, this transition is fully obscured by high overpotentials of reaction $V^{3+} \rightleftharpoons V^{4+}$. The final voltages under the current load corresponding to 50 % SOC are 1.61 and 1.86 V for the nanobed and ground GFE, respectively. The overall electric energy required to charge 4 ml of the working electrolyte to 50 % SOC was 827 J (0.229 Wh) and 1109 J (0.308 Wh) for the nanobed and the ground GFE, respectively. This energy was calculated by inte-

grating the electric power input over time according to $E = \int_{t=0}^t UI dt$

The energy needed for charging is about 30 % less in the case of the nanobed electrode. This difference underlines the positive effect of the nanostructured bed on the battery performance.

3.2.2. Short charge-discharge steps

The open circuit voltage (OCV) reached values around 1.376 V for both the nanobed and the ground GFE, which indicates comparable faradaic efficiency of both systems. Next, we characterized the systems by performing short-term charging and discharging steps with the following current sequence of +50/−50, +100/−100, +150/−150, +300/−300, +200/−500, and +200/−750 mA/cm². The positive and negative signs indicate charging and discharging steps, respectively.

Fig. 5. a) Polarization curves obtained from measuring fast charge/discharge steps at the flow rate of 2.5 cm/min: the solid lines connect experimental points, the dashed lines are the linear fits of the experimental data, the black asterisk represents the measured OCV; b) The dependence of the power density as a function of the passing current density.

Table 2

Initial ohmic resistances of the assembled battery and the energy required to charge the battery.

	$ASR_{in}^{imp} (\Omega \text{ cm}^2)$	$E \text{ (Wh)}$
UT-GFE	0.65 ± 0.04	0.283 ± 0.022
TT-GFE	0.52 ± 0.04	0.270 ± 0.008
MWCNT	0.46 ± 0.03	0.262 ± 0.006
f-MWCNT	0.57 ± 0.05	0.254 ± 0.005
FWCNT	0.37 ± 0.01	0.243 ± 0.003

Each current was applied for 120 s except for charging at the highest currents (500 and 750 mA/cm²) when the voltage needed was above 1.85 V. In those cases, we used a current of 200 mA/cm² for 150 and 225 s, respectively, to obtain the required SOC. An OCV measurement was taken between two successive charge/discharge steps. The measured quantity was the battery voltage as a function of time.

Fig. 4 shows the obtained results for both tested electrode systems of such a cycling experiment at an electrolyte flow rate of 2.5 cm/min, giving a volumetric flow rate of approximately 1 ml/min. The better performance of the nanostructured material is apparent. The over-voltages needed during the charging and discharging with nanobed (f-MWCNT based) are approximately 200 mV lower than those for the ground pristine GFE at the same current densities, implying the nanobed provides improved battery performance. This enhancement is reached

due to increased electrode surface area and probably enhanced catalytic activity, as discussed in Section 3.2.1.

Another interesting point is the dynamics of the charge and discharge steps. In the case of charging, both systems showed very similar dynamic behavior characterized by almost immediate adjustments in the battery voltage to the step changes in current (flat curves). The application of lower current densities in the later part of the measurement contributed to this behavior (500 and 750 mA/cm² were not used for charging due to exceeding the safety limit in voltage; see above). The discharge steps exhibited delayed voltage stabilization, especially at the highest discharge current densities. While the voltage almost immediately reached a constant value for the ground GFE, this dynamics was slower in the case of the nanobed. The steady voltage was attained at the end of the 2-minute discharge periods. This difference in the charge/discharge dynamics is probably associated with the structural arrangement of the nanobed. Possessing a large interfacial electrode-electrolyte area and, therefore, a high reaction rate may render the transport of the electroactive species into the nanobed the limiting step. The convective flow mainly occurs through the compressed graphite felt electrodes holding the nanobed in place. The transport of vanadium species into the nanobed may, thus, rely on both weakened convection through the nanobed and diffusion. The slower dynamics would then be explained by the gradual formation of the concentration gradients, driving the electroactive species transport to the proper parts. This feature of the nanobed implies that its geometry can be further improved.

Fig. 6. a) Initial ohmic resistances of the assembled batteries with various nanomaterials; b) charging curves averaged from three experiments for all tested materials (4 ml of the working electrolytes charged at 200 mA/cm² for 6175 s).

Fig. 7. Polarization curves evaluated at various linear velocities during battery discharge for a) untreated ground graphite felt electrode (UT-GFE), b) thermally-treated ground graphite felt electrode (TT-GFE), c) multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), d) carboxylated multiwalled carbon nanotubes (f-MWCNTs), and e) few-walled carbon nanotubes (FWCNTs). The points are the mean values from three independent experiments, and the error bars represent the standard deviation.

3.2.3. Polarization curves

The steady-state points from the charge/discharge steps were used to plot the polarization curves (voltage-current density curves) for both electrode arrangements (Fig. 5a) and their discharging power density-current density dependencies (Fig. 5b). Both graphs clearly show the enhanced performance of the nanobed when compared to the ground pristine GFE.

The polarization curves are virtually straight lines, implying constant system resistance. These curves were processed based on a method by Zawadzinski et al. [39], who qualitatively divided such curves into three regions representing (i) activation loss, (ii) ohmic loss, and (iii) transport loss in the battery. The first region corresponds to losses caused by electrode polarization due to limited kinetics of electrochemical reactions, the second one to losses due to either contact resistances and finite conductivity of electrolyte and membrane (measured as impedance at high frequency) or resistances associated with mass transfer within the electrodes, and the last one with limitations in bulk electrolyte delivery. The third region is generally caused by an insufficient supply of the electroactive species to the electrode. Since we did not observe the third region on our polarization curves, we do not discuss the aspects of such losses here. However, we evaluate both the overpotential associated with the activation loss (region 1) and the resistances associated with the ohmic loss (region 2).

The potential loss associated with region 1 is obtained as a difference between the measured OCV (black asterisk in Fig. 5a) and the potential found by prolonging the linear part of the polarization curve with the y-axis (red and blue dashed lines in Fig. 5a). We denote this potential loss as $\Delta\phi_1$. As can be seen from Fig. 5a, $\Delta\phi_1$ is virtually zero for the nanobed, while it is around 130 mV for the ground GFE. This result points to a limited electrocatalytic activity of the ground GFE towards the vanadium species. As will be apparent from the following text, the overpotential $\Delta\phi_1$ is the main cause for the worse performance of the ground GFE. Next, we evaluated the area-specific resistances (for the second linear region of the polarization curve) by taking the absolute value of the slopes of the polarization curves (linear fit of the experimental data). The evaluated battery ASRs are 1.53 and 1.62 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for the nanobed and ground GFE, respectively. When compared to the initial ohmic resistances (from high-frequency impedance measurements) of 0.61 and 0.71 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$, the resistances in the discharging battery are approximately 1 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ larger. The ASRs are relatively similar for both the nanobed and the ground GFE (the polarization curves are virtually parallel to each other; see Fig. 5a), implying the internal transport resistances are similar in both cases; the better performance of the nanobed is associated with the smaller resistance of the charge transfer at the electrode surface. The lower resistance of the electron transfer is given by the larger interfacial area provided by the nanobed and possibly auspicious catalytic effect of the chosen material.

3.3. Testing nanostructured materials

The previous section showed that creating a nanostructured bed between two graphite-felt electrode layers dramatically affects the battery characteristics and is worth pursuing. In this section, we test three nanostructured materials preselected from our previous study [28] and compare those to ground thermally treated and ground pristine GFES. Since we generated quite a substantial amount of data, we divided this section into three parts. The first part discusses the material behavior during electrolyte charging, the second focuses on the polarization curves obtained at various flow rates, and the last one quantitatively evaluates the performance of the tested materials. All the experiments described here were performed in triplicates, i.e., we created three beds for each material, always weighing out the corresponding amount and sandwiching it between the two pristine unground GFES. In this way, we included the errors associated with bed preparation in our result analysis.

Table 3

The activation potential loss $\Delta\phi_1$ and the ASRs evaluated from discharging polarization curves obtained at the tested flow rates. The last column shows the ohmic resistances measured before the electrolyte charging, which is given only for easy comparison.

Material	ASR_{in}^{imp} ($\Omega\text{ cm}^2$)	2.5 cm/min		7.3 cm/min		14.6 cm/min	
		$\Delta\phi_1$ (mV)	ASR ($\Omega\text{ cm}^2$)	$\Delta\phi_1$ (mV)	ASR ($\Omega\text{ cm}^2$)	$\Delta\phi_1$ (mV)	ASR ($\Omega\text{ cm}^2$)
UT-GFE	0.65 ± 0.04	56 ± 49	1.62 ± 0.02	56 ± 49	1.29 ± 0.06	55 ± 47	1.22 ± 0.07
TT-GFE	0.52 ± 0.04	9 ± 15	1.56 ± 0.10	10 ± 11	1.27 ± 0.06	8 ± 11	1.24 ± 0.07
MWCNT	0.46 ± 0.03	45 ± 45	1.66 ± 0.33	21 ± 38	1.29 ± 0.27	13 ± 22	1.11 ± 0.13
f-MWCNT	0.57 ± 0.45	-19 ± 7	1.54 ± 0.06	-12 ± 2	1.31 ± 0.04	-7 ± 4	1.2 ± 0.06
FWCNT	0.37 ± 0.01	-4 ± 6	1.09 ± 0.04	-3 ± 6	0.93 ± 0.02	-2 ± 5	0.90 ± 0.03

3.3.1. Electrolyte charging

The characterization of each prepared electrode proceeded according to the protocol above, i.e., (i) measuring the initial system resistance by high-frequency impedance measurement, (ii) charging the system to 50 % SOC, and (iii) performing a short charge-discharge characterization. In this section, we mainly focus on the first two steps that provide an initial estimate of the behavior of a given material as a 3D electrode in the battery. Specifically, we evaluate the initial ohmic battery resistance (before charging), the electric energy required for charging 4 ml of the vanadium solution to SOC of 50 %, and the battery resistance after charging. Table 2 contains the initial ohmic battery resistances evaluated from impedance measurements at high frequencies (R_{in}^{imp}) and the electric energy required to charge 4 ml of the vanadium solutions (E). The initial resistances are plotted in Fig. 6a. The charging curves are plotted in Fig. 6.

The charging curves have a dissimilar course for the individual tested materials. On the one hand, an almost constant voltage is necessary to charge the traditionally used graphite felt, both thermally treated (TT - orange curve in Fig. 6b) and pristine, i.e., untreated (UT - blue curve in Fig. 6b). On the other hand, the charging for the other materials exhibits a significant voltage increase during the first several tens of seconds (see the inset of Fig. 6b). The required charging voltage then grows slowly for MWCNT, and shows a further increase around 2000s for f-MWCNT. The initial dynamics in charging the electrolyte suggest differences in the structure of the electrodes formed by the ground felt and the nanomaterials. The missing initial voltage increase for the GFE materials indicates the charging process is not limited by the transport of electrochemical species but rather the proceeding electrochemical reactions. Since the ground GFE is characterized by relatively large structures (characteristic dimensions on the order of hundreds of micrometers), the created bed possesses large porosity, easily flowed through by the working electrolyte. Such an electrochemical limitation stems from a relatively small electrode surface area compared to nanomaterials and probably lower electrocatalytic activity [28]. Nanomaterials create beds of much lower porosity, hindering the convective transport through such a bed. The transport of electroactive species can, to a certain degree, rely on diffusive transport and the generation of concentration gradients inside the bed.

Although the three tested nanomaterials are CNTs, they exhibit different charging courses. While the charging voltage for MWCNTs has an almost constant voltage value and only slowly increases in time, the f-MWCNTs require a (relatively) small voltage during the first 2000 s, corresponding to the small overpotential needed for the reaction $V^{3+} \rightleftharpoons V^{4+}$ on this material. Interestingly, the curves for all materials except for FWCNTs eventually require voltage over 1.6 V for the charging process, indicating very similar final resistances for the main reactions proceeding in VRFB. FWCNTs exhibited the smallest required voltage to drive the charging almost for the whole charging time.

The results imply that each material has a different catalytic activity toward the vanadium reactions and offers different ohmic resistance and resistance associated with internal transfer. This feature, however, strongly affects the electric energy consumption needed to charge the electrolyte from its initial composition to 50 % SOC (see Table 2 - E

(Wh)). Using FWCNTs, one can save up to 15 % of energy for charging compared to graphite felt.

3.3.2. Polarization curves

After charging to 50 % SOC, all materials underwent short-term charging and discharging steps according to a preset sequence described in Section 3.2.2 at three different linear (superficial) velocities equal to 2.5, 7.3, and 14.6 cm/min. The last obtained points for each step, i.e., the measured battery voltage at a given current density, were used for plotting the polarization curves. Raw data from the polarization curve experiments for each material are available in the supplemental material in Figure S4. The evaluated polarization curves for all materials at all tested linear velocities are plotted in Fig. 7a-e. The polarization curves show the effect of the flow rate on the battery performance and the reproducibility of the experiments for individual materials. Quick inspection and comparison among materials also indicate which materials are suitable for the application.

Fig. 7 shows that the electrolyte flow rate significantly affects the overall battery performance. At the smallest tested linear velocity of 2.5 cm/min (red curve in all panes), the discharge polarization curves show the highest negative slope, meaning the battery loses its voltage fastest as a function of the drain current. This is evident for all tested materials. However, an increase in the flow rate to 7.3 and 14.6 cm/min positively affects the internal battery voltage loss. Interestingly, there are minimal changes between the polarization curves for these two linear velocities, suggesting that the battery performance is no longer improved by enhancing convective mass transfer. This is virtually true for TT-GFE and FWCNTs. The resistance is, therefore, mainly associated with diffusion and migration within the bed (and the initial system resistance). The difference between polarization curves measured at 7.3 cm and 14.7 cm/min for the other three tested materials, namely MWCNTs, UT-GFE, and f-MWCNTs, still show differences; however, much more minor than the differences between 2.5 and 7.3 cm/min, implying very similar effects to play a role in these materials.

To compare the materials directly from the polarization curves, we calculated the activation overpotential $\Delta\phi_1$ and the ASRs from the discharge polarization curves identically to Section 3.2.3. The data are given in Table 3 for all tested flow rates and materials. All materials, except for FWCNTs, have roughly the same ASRs (evaluated as slopes of linear U-j regions) at the given flow rates, which, when considering the initial ohmic resistance, is not surprising and suggests very similar internal limitations. This is illustrated in Figure S5, showing the polarization curves for all tested materials in a single plot. The resistance decreases upon increasing the linear velocity from 2.5 to 7.3 cm/min and then minimally changes when applying the highest linear velocity of 14.6 cm/min. The resistance is almost 30 % lower for the FWCNTs, confirming the dominant behavior of this material in the battery. Interestingly, the activation potential loss is negligible for FWCNTs, f-MWCNTs, and TT-GFE, unlike the other two materials, for which this overpotential is several tens of mV, affecting the material performance. These results show that the electrocatalytic properties of the materials play an essential role towards vanadium electrochemistry.

The observed differences between UT-GFE, TT-GFE, and carbon

Fig. 8. Power density as a function of the discharge current density for all the tested materials at liner velocities of a) 2.5 cm/min, b) 7.3 cm/min, and c) 14.6 cm/min.

nanotubes might be associated with the structure of the carbon materials. The first group comprises nonporous materials (UT-GFE, TT-GFE), stipulating electrochemical reactions occurring on the outer surface without the reactants diffusing into any nanoporous structure. Similarly, FWCNTs have tiny pores with a diameter of around 2.5–3 nm, precluding the pores from acting as a reacting surface. As depicted in Figure S4, the dynamics of discharging (and also charging) is relatively

Fig. 9. Voltaic efficiencies evaluated from the short-term cyclic experiments with applied current density of 150 mA/cm² at liner velocities of 2.5 cm/min, 7.3 cm/min, and 14.6 cm/min.

fast, quickly establishing a steady potential reading. Unlike these, MWCNTs and f-MWCNTs have diameters of 110–170 and 9.5 nm, allowing the internal exchange of vanadium species. The electrochemical reactions proceeding inside the pores might affect material behavior, manifested, e.g., in slower dynamics in charging and discharging (see Figure S4, compare, e.g., pane a) for UT-GFE and c) for MWCNT).

Interestingly, the results also indicate significant differences in the material properties, collectively manifested as the variability in the observed battery voltages at various discharge current densities. This variability is quantified through the plotted error bars, which show that MWCNTs are characterized by the lowest reproducibility (i.e., the differences between three prepared 3D electrodes), unlike, e.g., FWCNTs, at which the reproducibility is excellent. In this case, the error bars are virtually invisible. Although there is a possibility of human error during bed preparation, the material properties are the main source of the discrepancies. For example, the used MWCNTs purchased from Sigma Aldrich, although very cheap, are nanotubes with only 90 % purity, rendering themselves as a “fluff” of material difficult to handle. FWCNTs, being comparatively expensive, on the other hand, are delivered with a carbon purity larger than 95 % and turn out to be amendable to bed formation.

3.3.3. Power density and voltaic efficiency

Fig. 8 shows the evaluated power densities for the individual materials as a function of discharge current densities for the three tested flow rates. The Figure shows the dominance of the FWCNTs as the electrode material in vanadium redox flow batteries under tested conditions. Its maximum values reach 420, 505, and 510 mW/cm² for the linear velocities of 2.5, 7.3, and 14.6 cm/min. Compared to published results (e.g., 508 mW/cm² in [40], 550 mW/cm² [41], 510 mW/cm² [42]), these values are excellent. Albeit the comparison among various works is always troublesome due to large variations in the conditions under which the optimum power densities were obtained, the few walled nanotubes (FWCNTs) prove to be promising as an electrode material in vanadium redox flow batteries.

The performance of other materials was worse, although competitive characteristics were still found. Surprisingly, all the tested materials show similar characteristics, although pristine and thermally treated graphite felts performed a bit worse than MWCNTs and carboxylic-acid functionalized MWCNTs. This result is especially pronounced at the highest linear velocity. At 2.5 cm/min, the maximum power densities were obtained at a current density of 500 mA/cm² for all these materials, irrespective of the linear velocity. However, the tendency to shift to higher current densities with increasing linear velocity is visible.

We also evaluated the voltaic efficiency from the short charge-

discharge cycling performed in this work. Specifically, the voltaic efficiency was calculated by dividing the average discharge voltage by the average charge voltage measured at 150 mA/cm² for all three applied linear velocities. The obtained results are plotted in a bar graph in Fig. 9. According to the literature, a voltaic efficiency above 80 % indicates good battery performance [43]. Our calculations confirmed the superior performance of FWCNTs, which achieved a voltaic efficiency over 80 % for all measured velocities. In contrast, UT-GFE showed the poorest performance, barely reaching 70 % voltaic efficiency.

4. Conclusions

The sandwich structure of a flow-through electrode for vanadium redox flow batteries, comprising a (nano-)material bed and two compressing graphite felt electrodes, was advantageously used for fast testing of carbon nanotubes for theoretical application in VRFB. Such an electrode geometry exhibited reasonable pressure drops in the range of the electrolyte flow rates used and proved the beneficial incorporation of the nanostructured bed. Although further development is needed to implement such sandwiched electrodes in real applications, the system saves time in evaluating the potential of a nanomaterial, often available in minute amounts, for VRFB applications. Employing the developed system, we characterized several carbon nanotubes preselected from our previous study, which showed their promising electrochemical behavior in stationary vanadium electrolytes. Compared to a ground pristine graphite felt electrode as a benchmark, the carbon nanotubes performed better at applied flow rates except for the tested multiwalled CNTs (MWCNTs), displaying significant variations among prepared electrodes. The material dominating the study was few-walled carbon nanotubes (FWCNT), characterized by the lowest internal ohmic resistance, lowest electric energy required for its charging, and highest reachable discharging power density exceeding 500 mW/cm² at 50 % SOC and room temperature. Albeit focused on testing otherwise hard-to-characterize nanostructured materials for VRFBs, this concept of material screening can be easily extended to other electrochemical systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Štěpán Halada: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Václav Láznicka:** Investigation. **Tomáš Němec:** Investigation. **Petr Mazúr:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **Jiří Charvát:** Validation. **Zdeněk Slouka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the financial support of the European Regional Development Fund – project ORGBAT No.CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/16.025/0007445 and the project “The Energy Conversion and Storage”, funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2024.144681.

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